

"A STUDY ON MARKETING OF CATTLE FEED IN AKBARPUR DISTRICT OF UTTAR PRADESH."

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Abstract

This thesis aims to investigate the current state of cattle feed production and usage in the state of Uttar Pradesh, India. The study examines the types of feed commonly used for cattle, including both traditional and modern options, as well as their nutritional value and cost-effectiveness. Additionally, the research explores the factors that influence cattle feed choices, such as availability, accessibility, and cultural practices. The study is based on a mixed-methods approach, which involves both qualitative and quantitative data collection and analysis. The qualitative data is obtained through interviews with cattle farmers, feed suppliers, and industry experts. The quantitative data is gathered through a survey of a representative sample of cattle farmers in Akbarpur district of Uttar Pradesh. The findings of the study reveal that traditional feed options such as hay, straw, and crop residues remain popular among cattle farmers due to their low cost and availability. However, there is a growing trend towards the use of modern feed options such as concentrated feed, minerals, and vitamins, which are considered to be more nutritious and efficient. The study also reveals that the choice of cattle feed is influenced by several factors such as the farmer's income level, the type of cattle being raised, and the availability of feed ingredients. The research concludes that there is a need to promote the use of modern feed options among cattle farmers in Akbarpur district of Uttar Pradesh, while also preserving traditional feed options that are deeply rooted in local culture and practices. Additionally, the study recommends the development of policies and programs that support the production and distribution of high-quality cattle feed, as well as the education and training of cattle farmers on optimal feeding practices.

Keywords: Marketing, Cattle Feed, Constraints, Garrett Ranking Techniques.

Introduction

The dairy sector is the largest single agricultural commodity with a 4% share in the economy. India is globally the largest producer of milk, with a production of around 188 million MT productions in 2019-20. Indian milk production is expected to grow to 270 MMT by 2025. In terms of India's Export of Dairy products, during the year 2020-21, was 54,762.31 MT to the world for Rs. 1,491.66 crores i.e., \$201.37 Million. The major exporting destinations for 2020-21 were UAE, Bangladesh, and other Southeast Asian countries. Uttar Pradesh, a state that houses as much as 16.17% of India's population depends on agriculture and allied activities for economic development. The State has set a record in the dairy sector by contributing the highest in India's milk production. The production of milk in the State has gradually increased. In the last four years, Uttar Pradesh produced 1,242.37 lakh metric tonnes of milk. Milk production in UP increased from 277.697 lakh metric tonnes in 2016-17, to 318.630 lakh metric tons in 2019-20.

The dairy and animal husbandry sector contributes around 4.2% of India's GDP. It is a primary source of income for about 7 crore rural families. Most of the milk producers are landless or small and marginal farmers. For more than two decades, India has been the largest milk producer in the world. In 2018-19, India produced 176.4 million tonnes (MT) of milk, about 20% of the world's milk production. The Compounded Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) in the last 20 years was 4.5%. The world's milk production in the meanwhile grew by around 2%. The cattle feed market in India has experienced significant growth in recent years, driven by factors such as increasing demand for milk and milk products, rising disposable incomes, and a growing population of livestock. Cattle feed refers to the food given to cows, buffaloes, and other livestock for their growth, development, and productivity. It is an essential component of the livestock industry and plays a crucial role in ensuring the health and well-being of cattle.

The Indian cattle feed market is largely dominated by the organized sector, which includes large players such as Amul, Godrej Agrovet, and Cargill. However, the market also has a significant presence of small and unorganized players, especially in rural areas. The demand for cattle feed is driven by the dairy sector, which is the largest consumer of cattle feed in India. The Indian dairy industry is the largest in the world, and it is expected to continue to grow at a steady pace, providing significant

opportunities for the cattle feed market.

The Indian government has also been actively promoting the cattle feed industry, with various initiatives such as the National Livestock Mission, which aims to promote livestock development and improve the availability of quality feed and fodder. The government has also encouraged the use of modern technology and innovative practices to increase the efficiency and productivity of the livestock sector, further driving the demand for cattle feed.

Material And Methods**Selection of Market Functionaries:****Selection of District:**

There are 75 districts in Uttar Pradesh. Out of these 75 districts, Akbarpur was selected purposively on the basis of one of the high cattle feed consumption. The Akbarpur district consists of 5 Tehsils with a total area of 2,485 km sq, has 8 Blocks, 734 Gram Panchayats, 1300 villages, 16 Police Stations, 4 Nagar Palikas. Akbarpur is situated between 25.2605° N, 83.2645° E.

Selection of Block:

There are a total 8 blocks in Akbarpur district. They are Baskhari, Bhiti, Bhiyaon, Jahageerganj, Jalalpur, Katehari, Ramnagar, Tanda. Out of these blocks Baskhari blocks was purposively selected for research work.

Selection of Village:

There was about 1300 villages in Akbarpur in which 176 villages were in Bhiti block. Out of these 5% villages were selected randomly for the study.

Selection of Respondent:

With the assistance of the gram panchayat, a list of all farmers was created. Following that, a list of all farmers and respondent was created in ascending order, and farmers were divided into groups based on the size of their land holdings.

The market functionaries were randomly selected for the study purpose. Out of total market functionary's 1 percent functionaries was selected randomly.

Tool Used for Analysis:**Garrett ranking techniques:**

Garrett's Ranking Technique was applied to study the preference, change of orders of constraints and advantages into numerical scores. The prime advantage of this technique over simple frequency distribution is that the constraints are arranged based on their severity from the point of view of respondents. The orders of

merit given by the respondents were converted in to rank by suing the formula. To find out the most significant factor which influences the respondent, Garrett's ranking technique was used. This tool will use to identify the constraints. As per this method, respondents have been asked to assign the rank for all factors and the outcomes of such ranking have been converted into score

Result And Discussion

SI. NO.	Constraints Perceived	Garrett score	Garrett rank
1.	Lack of market information	96	VII
2.	Unorganized marketing system	91	VIII
3.	Absence of minimum support price	87	IX
4.	Inadequate of appropriate credit facilities	85	V
5.	Risky Investment	83	VI
6.	Availability of product	81	IV
7.	Fluctuations in price	79	I
8.	Knowledge of quality	78	II
9.	High Competition	77	III

Constraints restricting against marketing of cattle feed

This following table reveals about the constraints restricting against marketing of Cattle Feed in which Fluctuations in price rank I and Absence of minimum support price rank IX.

Summary And Conclusion:

Study reveals about the constraints restricting against marketing of Cattle Feed in which Fluctuations in price rank I, Knowledge of quality rank II, High Competition rank III, Availability of product rank IV, Inadequate of appropriate credit facilities rank V, Risky Investment rank VI, Lack of market information rank VII, Unorganized marketing system rank VIII, and Absence of minimum support price rank IX. In current scenario and future of Cattle Feed have bright future. Farmers depend on the Cattle Feed that show the increasing demand of the Cattle Feed. Due to the use of the Cattle Feed farmers yield more milk so they not stop to use the Cattle Feed. Cattle Feed are less time taken to feed and safe to use. According to farmer without cattle feed milk production are less.

value with the help of the following formula.

$$\text{Percentage} = 100 * (\text{RIJ} - 0.50) / \text{NJ}$$

Where,

R_{ij} is the rank given to ith item by the jth individual, N_{jj} is the number of items ranked by the jth individual.

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